

Studies on the Dependence of Optical Rotatory Power on Chemical Constitution. Part X. The Rotatory Dispersion of Stereoisomeric Phenyl and Iodophenyl Derivatives of Iminocamphors and Aminocamphors.*

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The relation between chemical constitution and rotatory power which is investigated in the present paper is that of position isomerism and rotatory dispersion in the aryl derivatives of iminocamphors and aminocamphors, the former being obtained by the condensation of the three stereoisomeric camphorquinones (*d*, *l*, *dl*) with aniline and iodoaniline (*o*, *m*, *p*), and the latter from the former by reduction.

o-Iodoaniline and *d*-camphorquinone are found to give three forms of *o*-iodophenyliminocamphor melting at 86° (*α*), 93° (*β*) and 97° (*γ*) respectively according to the temperature of reaction and the process of crystallisation (*vide* Experimental). The conversion of the *α*-form into the *γ*-form with or without a trace of the latter and that of the *β*-form into the *γ*-modification only in the presence of a trace of the *γ*-form by heat show that these forms are three distinct substances and not impure specimens of one and the same substance. This is also borne out by their analytical data and the identical values of their rotatory power in different solvents (Table III).

These forms are shown to be polymorphic by the method developed by one of us (Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 1007), which is based on the determination of their dispersion. The values of

* This work was originally undertaken jointly with Messrs. Mahan Singh and Raghunath Rai, but before it had advanced appreciably this collaboration ceased on account of their having left this laboratory.

rotatory dispersion are identical for polymorphous modifications, whereas the values are different for isomeric (or tautomeric) modifications.

Some interesting examples of the influence of substituents on the course of a reaction were encountered in dealing with the stereoisomeric *o*-iodophenylaminocamphors. It was found that no hydrochlorides were produced by saturating their ethereal solutions with hydrogen chloride. The *meta* and *para* isomerides readily yielded hydrochlorides under this treatment. In this respect the behaviour is similar to that of 2:4:6-trichloro-3-iodoaniline which also does not give the hydrochloride by saturating its alcoholic solution with hydrogen chloride (McCombie and Ward, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 1995). The inhibitive action of the two *ortho* substituents on the production of a derivative is also seen in the halogen substituted phenols (Brazier and McCombie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 968). The results are quite satisfactory when one at least of the *ortho* positions relative to the hydroxyl groups is unsubstituted. The failure to form a hydrochloride met with *o*-iodophenylaminocamphor in which one of the *ortho*-positions is free, must be, therefore, attributed to the steric hindrance reinforced by the camphoryl group replacing one of the hydrogen atoms of the amino-group. The sign of the rotatory power of *p*-iodophenylaminocamphors is reversed when the bases are converted into their acetyl derivatives: $+89.64^\circ$ to -23.49° for $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}(\text{green})}$ (in chloroform). A similar reversal of sign on acetylation has been observed already in the case of *p*-phenylene-bisaminocamphor (Singh and Bhaduri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 545). The reversal of the sign of rotatory power in the latter example was explained and correlated with the saturation of a lone pair of electrons on the acyl oxygen and a similar explanation seems feasible in the present case and is shown in the following formula by the postulation of a "dative bond" (Menzies, *Nature*, 1928, 121, 457) between the acyl oxygen atom and the hydrogen atom attached to the asymmetric carbon atom (C).

This reversal of sign of rotatory power is exhibited in the graphs of rotatory dispersion of the *dextro*- and *laevo*-isomerides (Fig. I).

FIG. 1.

Rotatory dispersion of acetyl derivative of p-iodophenylaminocamphor (d & l).

The reversal of sign of rotatory power of a derivative may also be explained from the polarity of the substituents. The optical activity of the parent amino-compound may be regarded as being largely governed by the secondary amino-group which is attached to the asymmetric carbon atom. This group is of the electropositive or electron-repelling type; its optical influence (positive rotation) will be increased by the introduction of another group of the same character, and diminished (and even reversed in sign) by the introduction of a group of the opposite polar character, such as acyl group and is shown in the following scheme (the direction of electron shift being indicated by an arrow):

The Influence of Solvent on the Rotatory Power.—The solvents employed in this work in the decreasing order of their dielectric constants are methyl alcohol > ethyl alcohol > acetone > chloroform > ether > benzene. A reference to tables of rotatory power will

show that the sequence of solvents in order of decreasing (or increasing) rotatory power is quite different from that of their dielectric constants. The rotatory power of the derivatives of phenyliminocamphor is highest in benzene (with a slight deviation in the case of *o*-iodophenyliminocamphor) which has the lowest dielectric constant, but this regularity does not extend to the derivatives of phenylaminocamphor (Table A). The rotatory power of all the compounds is lower in methyl alcohol than in ethyl alcohol, whereas the order of their dielectric constants runs in the opposite direction. The rotatory power of a compound does not bear any simple relation to the dielectric constant of the solvent in which it is dissolved is evident from the rotation values of phenylaminocamphor and its derivatives in chloroform (Table A). The rotatory powers are highest in chloroform with a slight deviation in the case of the *meta*-compound, whereas the value of dielectric constant stands intermediate in the series.

The Influence of Position and Nature of the Substituent on the Rotatory Power.—The order of the rotatory power of the derivatives of phenyliminocamphor in the six solvents is $p > \text{unsubstituted} > m > o$, whereas in the case of derivatives of phenylaminocamphor this order is $m > \text{unsubstituted} > p > o$ (Table A). The order predicted from Frankland's "lever arm" theory (Frankland and Wharton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, **69**, 1583), namely, $p > m > \text{unsubstituted} > o$, is followed in the derivatives of phenyliminocamphor, except for the inverted relationship of the *meta*- and the *unsubstituted* compound. This regularity disappears in the derivatives of phenylaminocamphor in which the observed order $m > \text{unsubstituted} > p > o$ does not agree with this theory. The rule of Cohen (Cohen and Dudley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **97**, 1733; Cohen, *ibid*, 1911, **99**, 1058) which states that the rotatory effect of the *ortho*-grouping differs more from that of the phenyl than do those of *meta*- and *para*-groupings, is followed in both the series. The conception of a mechanical moment in the "lever arm" theory of Frankland is being replaced by that of an electrostatic moment. The introduction of a polar group into a hydrocarbon molecule is compared to the insertion of an electrostatic doublet, which according to the nature of the substituent may be oriented with either its positive or negative end towards the parent molecule (Thomson, *Phil. Mag.*, 1923, [vi], **46**, 497). Thomson has discussed the problem from a theoretical

TABLE A.

Name of the compound.	Benzene.	Ether.	Chloroform.	Acetone.	Ethyl alcohol.	Methyl alcohol.
Phenylaminocamphor.	(2.28)* 2192°	(4.3) 1925°	(5.2) 2153°	(21.5) 1963°	(25.8) 2007°	(31.2) 1940°
<i>o</i> -Iodophenylaminocamphor.	1093	863.5	983	1110	907.9	915
<i>m</i> -Iodophenylaminocamphor.	1907	1602	1771	1664	1710	1650
<i>p</i> -Iodophenylaminocamphor.	2462	2080	2380	2122	2193	2164
The order of rotatory power: $p > unsubstituted > m > o$						
Phenylaminocamphor.	337.3	336.4	355.3	307.2	298.2	277.1
<i>o</i> -Iodophenylaminocamphor.	163.8	238.5	285.1	224.2	209.7	183.1
<i>m</i> -Iodophenylaminocamphor.	405.1	418.9	405.0	323.1	318.9	299.8
<i>p</i> -Iodophenylaminocamphor.	316.2	307.9	330.2	298.4	266.2	262.8
The order of rotatory power: $m > unsubstituted > p > o$						

* Dielectric constant is given within brackets below the names of the solvents.

standpoint, and concludes that with two substituents of similar polarity, the electrostatic moments should be in the order $o > m$, *unsubstituted* nucleus $> p$, and with two substituents of opposite polarity in the order $p > m$, *unsubstituted* $> o$. If the conception of mechanical moment is replaced by that of an electrostatic moment, the influence of a substituent on the optical rotation of a parent compound will be dependent in sign and magnitude on the change in electrostatic moment, and will either be of the order $p > m > o$, or, $o > m > p$, and not in the former sequence alone as required by the suggestion of Frankland. The agreement between the experimental and the predicted order is exact in the case of derivatives of phenyliminocamphor, but the displacement of *meta* and the *unsubstituted* compounds in the derivatives of phenylaminocamphor cannot be accounted for.

The Influence of Chemical Constitution on the Rotatory Dispersion.—The substances investigated in the present paper show two types of rotatory dispersion, namely, "simple" and "complex." Phenyliminocamphor shows simple rotatory dispersion in all the solvents (except ethyl alcohol), whereas phenylaminocamphor exhibits complex rotatory dispersion (Tables I and II). *o*-Iodophenyliminocamphor shows simple dispersion in two solvents only namely, methyl alcohol and benzene, but its reduction product, *o*-iodophenylaminocamphor, possesses simple rotatory dispersion in all the solvents (Tables III and IV). The *meta*- and *para*-isomerides of both the series give simple rotatory dispersion in some solvents, and complex rotatory dispersion in others (Tables V to VIII). The rotatory dispersion of camphorquinones is simple in all the solvents (Table X; compare also Lowry and Cutter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 604). It is thus clear from the analysis of the above mentioned compounds that the type of rotatory dispersion which a substance exhibits depends also on the nature of the solvent in which it is dissolved. The acetyl derivatives of *p*-iodophenylaminocamphors are interesting as they seem to obey exactly Biot's law of inverse squares, $[\alpha] = k/\lambda^2$ (Table IX). Experience hitherto has shown that this law was never obeyed exactly, although some substances such as sodium tartrate (Lowry and Austin, *Phil. Trans.*, 1922, A, 222, 249) and octyl oxalate (Lowry and Richards, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1593) obey it very nearly.

The Physical Identity of Enantiomers.—In Parts VIII and IX of this series of investigations, it has been shown that the rotatory

power of the *dextro*- and *laevo*-enantiomers is identical in magnitude. The values of rotatory power recorded in Tables I to X further support Pasteur's fundamental principle of molecular dissymmetry according to which the *d*- and *l*-forms are represented as true mirror images of one another, differing in sign but absolutely identical in the numerical magnitude of the rotatory power.

The melting points of the inactive forms in both the series (with the exception of the *ortho*-isomerides) are higher than those of the active isomers. This shows that the inactive forms in those cases are, in the solid state, true racemates.

EXPERIMENTAL.

o-Iodophenylimino-*d*-camphor.

There are three polymorphic modifications of this substance: α (m.p. 87°), β (m.p. 93°) and γ (m. p. 97°).

β -Modification, m. p. 93° .—Molecular proportions of *o*-iodoaniline and *d*-camphorquinone were mixed together with two or three times the weight of anhydrous sodium sulphate and the mixture heated at 90 — 97° for about four hours. The substance was extracted with alcohol and on the addition of water an oil came down. The oil on being repeatedly dissolved in alcohol and reprecipitated with water, solidified to a yellow substance. It was recrystallised as yellow prisms (m. p. 93°) by dissolving it in the least possible quantity of hot alcohol and stirring the solution during cooling. (Found: C, 52.31, 52.17; H, 4.99, 5.22. $C_{16}H_{18}ONI$ requires C, 52.31; H, 4.91 per cent.).

α -Modification, m. p. 86 – 87° .—The lowest melting form is obtained on condensing *d*-camphorquinone and *o*-iodoaniline in molecular proportions in the presence of anhydrous sodium sulphate at 80 — 85° . The product of condensation is extracted with hot alcohol, the solution cooled *undisturbed* in an ice-bath, when light yellow prisms, m. p. 87° , are deposited. It is extremely soluble in chloroform, readily soluble in carbon disulphide, less so in ether, glacial acetic acid and benzene, still less in acetone, sparingly soluble in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 52.01; 52.02; H, 4.93; 4.83. $C_{16}H_{18}ONI$ requires C, 52.31; H, 4.91 per cent.).

γ -Modification, m. p. 97° .—The highest melting form is obtained when a saturated alcoholic solution of the form, m. p. 87° , is boiled

for a few minutes, cooled and precipitated with water. It is deposited as yellow prisms, m. p. 97° . It is, however, more conveniently obtained by heating for a few minutes the α -form or for a longer period the intermediate melting form (β) at 75 — 80° with a trace of the highest melting form (obtained from a previous operation), or by heating the α -form alone near its melting point for a longer period. (Found: C, 52.24, 52.13; H, 5.35; 5.25. $C_{16}H_{18}ONI$ requires C, 52.31; H, 4.91 per cent.). The rotatory powers of the three forms are recorded in (Table III).

o-Iodophenylimino-*l*-camphor was prepared in a similar way as the corresponding *dextro*-isomeride but was isolated in one modification only, namely, that melting at 93° . (Found: C, 52.13; H, 5.25. $C_{16}H_{18}ONI$ requires C, 52.31; H, 4.91 per cent.). The rotatory power in different solvents is identical with that of *d*-isomeride (Table III).

o-Iodophenylimino-*dl*-camphor was obtained in a similar way as its optically active isomerides and recrystallised out of alcohol as long yellow rectangular prisms melting at 85° . It had similar solubility in organic media as the optically active forms. (Found: C, 52.0; H, 5.11. $C_{16}H_{18}ONI$ requires C, 52.31; H, 4.91 per cent.).

o-Iodophenylamino-*d*-camphor was prepared in the usual way by the reduction of the three polymorphic modifications of *o*-iodophenylimino-*d*-camphor described above (in ether solution) with 10% potassium hydroxide solution and zinc dust, and was thrice crystallised out of alcohol as flat transparent prisms melting at 147 — 48° . The mixed melting point of the specimens obtained from the three polymorphic modifications was also 147 — 48° showing that all of them are one and the same compound.

It is extremely soluble in ether and chloroform, readily soluble in carbon disulphide and benzene, less so in acetone, fairly soluble in methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 52.48; H, 5.51. $C_{16}H_{20}ONI$ requires C, 51.03; H, 5.44 per cent.). The order of rotatory power in different solvents (Table IV) is as:—

Chloroform > ether > acetone > ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol > benzene.

o-Iodophenylamino-*d*-camphor does not yield a hydrochloride when its ethereal solution is saturated with hydrochloric acid gas.

o-Iodophenylamino-*l*-camphor was obtained in the usual way as colourless prisms melting at 148°. It had the same solubility as its *d*-isomeride. (Found: C, 51.99; H, 5.64. $C_{16}H_{20}ONI$ requires C, 52.03; H, 5.42 per cent.). The rotatory power is identical with that of the *d*-isomeride (Table IV). The *l*-base also does not yield the hydrochloride.

o-Iodophenylamino-*dl*-camphor was obtained in the usual way as its two optically active isomerides, as rectangular plates melting at 144-45°. (Found: C, 51.96; H, 5.59. $C_{16}H_{20}ONI$ requires C, 52.03; H, 5.42 per cent.). The *dl*-base, like its optically active isomerides, does not yield a hydrochloride.

m-Iodophenylimino-*d*-camphor.—This substance was obtained by heating *d*-camphorquinone and *m*-iodoaniline (in molecular proportions) together with an excess of anhydrous sodium sulphate in the usual way, as yellow prisms melting at 112-13°. The solubility of this substance in different solvents is of the same order as that of its *ortho*-isomeride. (Found: C, 52.18; H, 5.12. $C_{16}H_{18}ONI$ requires C, 52.31; H, 4.91 per cent.). The order of rotatory power in different solvents (Table V) is:

Benzene > chloroform > ethyl alcohol > acetone > methyl alcohol > ether.

The *l*-isomeride was prepared in a similar way from *l*-camphorquinone and has the same melting point and solubility as the *d*-isomeride. (Found: C, 52.20; H, 5.33. $C_{16}H_{18}ONI$ requires C, 52.31; H, 4.91 per cent.). The rotatory power is identical with that of the *d*-isomeride (Table V).

m-Iodophenylimino-*dl*-camphor was prepared in the same way as the optically active isomerides, and was crystallised out of 70 per cent alcohol as light yellow prisms melting at 116°. It is readily soluble in chloroform, benzene and acetone; less so in ether, moderately soluble in methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 52.07; H, 5.05. $C_{16}H_{18}ONI$ requires C, 52.31; H, 4.91 per cent.).

m-Iodophenylamino-*d*-camphor.—This was prepared in the usual way by the reduction of *m*-iodophenylimino-*d*-camphor and was obtained as prismatic needles melting at 109-110°. Its solubility in different solvents is in the same order as that of the *ortho*-isomeride. (Found: C, 51.75; H, 5.85. $C_{16}H_{20}ONI$ requires C, 52.03; H, 5.42 per cent.). The order of rotatory power in different solvents (Table VI) is as ether > benzene > chloroform > acetone >

ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol. The *hydrochloride* of the above base was prepared by saturating its ethereal solution with dry hydrochloric acid gas. (Found: Cl, 8.68. $C_{16}H_{21}ONICl$ requires Cl, 8.64 per cent.). Water decomposes the hydrochloride into the original base and free hydrochloric acid.

m-Iodophenylamino-l-camphor was prepared in a similar way as the corresponding *d*-isomeride and has the same melting point and solubility. (Found: C, 52.07; H, 5.94. $C_{16}H_{20}ONI$ requires C, 52.03; H, 5.42 per cent.). The magnitude of the rotatory power is identical with that of the *d*-compound (Table VI). The hydrochloride of the *l*-base was prepared in the same way as that of the *d*-isomeride and has similar properties. (Found: Cl, 8.53. $C_{16}H_{21}ONICl$ requires Cl, 8.64 per cent.).

m-Iodophenylamino-dl-camphor was prepared in a similar way as its two optically active isomeride and crystallised as transparent rectangular prisms melting at 123°. It is very readily soluble in acetone, benzene, and chloroform, less so in ether, sparingly soluble in methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 51.83; H, 5.55. $C_{16}H_{20}ONI$ requires C, 52.03; H, 5.42 per cent.). *m-Iodophenylamino-dl-camphor hydrochloride* prepared in the usual way, melted at 162°. (Found: Cl, 8.32. $C_{16}H_{21}ONICl$ requires Cl, 8.64 per cent.).

p-Iodophenylimino-d-camphor was obtained from *d*-camphorquinone and *p*-iodoaniline (molecular proportions) in the usual way and was recrystallised from 80% alcohol as flat prisms melting at 113-114°. It is extremely soluble in chloroform, less so in carbon disulphide, ether, glacial acetic acid, benzene and acetone, sparingly soluble in methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 52.33; H, 4.91; N, 4.07. $C_{16}H_{18}ONI$ requires C, 52.31; H, 4.91; N, 3.80 per cent.). The order of rotatory power in different solvents (Table VII) is benzene > chloroform > ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol > acetone > ether.

The *l*-isomeride was prepared in a similar way and has the same melting point and solubility. (Found: C, 52.22; H, 5.41. $C_{16}H_{18}ONI$ requires C, 52.31; H, 4.91 per cent.). The rotatory power is identical with that of the *d*-isomeride (Table VII).

p-Iodophenylimino-dl-camphor, prepared in a similar way as the corresponding *d*- and *l*-compounds, was recrystallised out of 70% alcohol as yellow rectangular prisms melting at 132°. It is readily soluble in acetone, benzene and chloroform, less so in ether, methyl

alcohol and ethyl alcohol and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 52.13; H, 4.90. $C_{16}H_{18}ONI$ requires C, 52.31; H, 4.91 per cent.).

p-Iodophenylamino-*d*-camphor was prepared from *p*-iodophenyl-imino-*d*-camphor in the same way as the other two position isomerides and was obtained as flat prisms melting at 113-14°. It is extremely soluble in ether and chloroform, readily soluble in carbon disulphide and benzene, fairly soluble in acetone, methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 51.91; H, 5.47. $C_{16}H_{20}ONI$ requires C, 52.03; H, 5.42 per cent.). The order of rotatory power in solvents (Table VIII) is chloroform > benzene > ether > acetone > ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol. The hydrochloride was obtained in the usual way as fine colourless needles melting at 125-26°. (Found: Cl, 8.14. $C_{16}H_{20}ONI, HCl$ requires Cl, 8.64 per cent.). It is resolved into hydrochloric acid and the free base by the addition of water.

p-Iodophenylamino-*l*-camphor was prepared (from *l*-camphor-quinone) in the same way as the corresponding *d*-isomeride and has the same melting point and solubility. (Found: C, 51.93; H, 5.64. $C_{16}H_{20}ONI$ requires C, 52.03; H, 5.42 per cent.). The rotatory power is identical with that of the *d*-isomeride within experimental error (Table VIII). *p*-Iodophenylamino-*l*-camphor hydrochloride was prepared in the usual way. (Found: Cl, 8.28. $C_{16}H_{20}ONI, HCl$ requires Cl, 8.64 per cent.).

p-Iodophenylamino-*dl*-camphor was prepared in the same way as the corresponding *d*- and *l*-compound, and was crystallised out of alcohol as transparent prisms melting at 160°. It is very readily soluble in chloroform, benzene, and acetone, less so in ether, somewhat sparingly soluble in methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 52.06; H, 5.59. $C_{16}H_{20}ONI$ requires C, 52.03; H, 5.42 per cent.). The hydrochloride obtained by saturating an ethereal solution of the base with hydrochloric acid gas melted at 127°. (Found: Cl, 18.41. $C_{16}H_{20}ONICl$ requires Cl, 8.64 per cent.).

The acetyl derivative of *p*-iodophenylamino-*d*-camphor was prepared by heating *p*-iodophenylamino-*d*-camphor (1 g.) with acetic anhydride (1.2 g.) at 160° for one hour and obtained as hexagonal plates, melting at 117-118° (yield 50 per cent.). It is freely soluble in the ordinary organic media. (Found: C, 52.39; H, 5.62. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2NI$ requires C, 52.56; H, 5.35 per cent.).

The rotatory power was observed in chloroform and is recorded in Table IX.

The *l*-iso meride was prepared in a similar way from *p*-iodophenylamino-*l*-camphor and has the same melting point and solubility. (Found: C, 52.26; H, 5.62. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2NI$ requires C, 52.56; H, 5.35 per cent.). The rotatory power is identical in numerical value with that of the *d*-isomeride (Table IX).

Phenylimino-l-camphor.—*l*-Camphorquinone and aniline in molecular proportions were heated together in the presence of fused anhydrous sodium sulphate on the water-bath till the product on cooling became a hard mass. It was crystallised out of alcohol as long yellow needles melting at 107-108°. It is readily soluble in acetone, chloroform and benzene; less so in ether, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and petroleum ether and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 79.73; H, 8.15. $C_{16}H_{19}ON$ requires C, 79.68; H, 7.58 per cent.). The rotatory power of the *dextro*- and *laevo*- compounds are identical (Table I).

Phenylimino-dl-camphor, prepared from *dl*-camphorquinone in the same way as the *laevo*-isomeride, after recrystallisation from 60 per cent. alcohol, as yellow prismatic needles, melted at 124°. (Found: N, 5.95. $C_{16}H_{19}ON$ requires N, 5.81 per cent.)

Phenylamino-l-camphor.—This was prepared in the usual way by the reduction of phenylimino-*l*-camphor and was crystallised as flat transparent prisms melting at 80°. It is readily soluble in benzene, chloroform, and ether, sparingly soluble in methyl alcohol, and ethyl alcohol, still less so in petroleum ether and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 79.04; H, 8.89. $C_{16}H_{21}ON$ requires C, 79.01; H, 8.64 per cent.).

The rotatory power of the *dextro*- and *laevo*-isomerides are equal in magnitude and the order in different solvents (Table II) is as chloroform > benzene > ether > acetone, ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol.

The *dextro-hydrochloride* obtained in the usual way from the *d*-base melts at 175°. (Found: Cl, 12.56. $C_{16}H_{21}ON, HCl$ requires Cl, 12.70 per cent.).

The *laevo-salt* also melts at 175°. (Found: Cl, 12.70. $C_{16}H_{21}ON, HCl$, requires Cl, 12.70 per cent.).

Phenylamino-dl-camphor, prepared in the usual way, by the reduction of phenylimino-*dl*-camphor, was recrystallised out of hot alcohol as colourless plates melting at 104-105°. (Found: C, 78.96; H, 8.52; N, 5.83. $C_{16}H_{21}ON$ requires C, 79.00; H, 8.64; N, 5.76 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* was obtained by saturating the ethereal solution of *dl*-phenylaminocamphor with hydrochloric acid gas as a white precipitate melting at 170—171°. (Found: N, 5.26. $C_{16}H_{21}ON$, HCl requires N, 5.21 per cent.)

The rotatory power determinations were made in a 2-dcm. jacketed tube at 35°. $Hg_{vio.}$, $Hg_{gr.}$, $Hg_{yel.}$ and Na_D refer to the violet mercury line 4358, the green mercury line 5461, the yellow mercury line 5780, and the sodium line 5893 respectively. The value of λ_0 , calculated from the dispersion formula is given in the tables, and is expressed as μ or 10^{-4} cm.

TABLE I.
Phenyliminocamphor.

Solvent.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.	[M]		
		Na_D	$Hg_{yel.}$	$Hg_{gr.}$
<i>Ether</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{110.69}{\lambda^2 - 0.1595}$;	$[M] = 2.41 [\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.3994\mu$		
Dextro	0.7148	+1424°	+1526°	+1927°
Laevo	0.7068	-1420	-1524	-1923
Mean (obs.)		1422	1525	1925
Calc.		1424	1528	1923
Diff.		-2	-3	+2
<i>Methyl alcohol</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{110.08}{\lambda^2 - 0.1621}$;	$[M] = 2.41 [\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.4026\mu$		
Dextro	0.6864	+1436	+1546	+1941
Laevo	0.6820	-1442	-1547	-1938
Mean (obs.)		1439	1547	1940
Calc.		1432	1543	1949
Diff.		+7	+4	-9
<i>Acetone</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{117.11}{\lambda^2 - 0.1543}$;	$[M] = 2.41 [\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.3928\mu$		
Dextro	0.6992	+1462°	+1570°	+1964°
Laevo	0.6952	-1455	-1567	-1961
Mean (obs.)		1459	1569	1963
Calc.		1462	1570	1961
Diff.		-3	-1	+2

Solvent.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.	[M]			
		Na _D	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}	
<i>Chloroform</i> $[\alpha] = \frac{125.56}{\lambda^2 - 0.1576}$; [M] = 2.41[α] ; λ ₀ = 0.3970.					
Dextro	0.6972	+1597	+1716°	+2153°	
Laevo	0.4964	-1590	-1716	-2153	
Mean (obs.)		1594	1716	2153	
Calc.		1596	1715	2153	
Diff.		-2	+1	+0	
<i>Benzene</i> $[\alpha] = \frac{126.15}{\lambda^2 - 0.1595}$; [M] = 2.41[α] ; λ ₀ = 0.3994.					
Dextro	0.7124	+1622	+1741	+2195	
Laevo	0.6876	-1621	-1735	-2189	
Mean (obs.)		1622	1738	2192	
Calc.		1619	1741	2192	
Diff.		+3	-3	+0	
<i>Ethyl alcohol</i>	0.6944	<i>d</i>	+1489	+1605	+2009
	0.7100	<i>l</i>	-1494	-1603	-2004
		mean	1492	1604	2007

TABLE II.

Phenylaminocamphor.

Solvent.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Dextro, laevo, or mean.	[M]			
			Na _D	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}	Hg _{vio.}
<i>Methyl alcohol</i>	0.6096	<i>d</i>	+235.3°	+243.2°	+277.1°	+492.3°
	0.5572	<i>l</i>	-233.3	-241.9	-277.1	-497.1
		mean	234.3	242.5	277.1	494.7
<i>Ethyl alcohol</i>	0.6140	<i>d</i>	+263.2	+267.1	+298.8	+526.4
	0.5512	<i>l</i>	-257.9	-266.8	-297.6	-530.4
		mean	260.6	267.0	298.2	528.4
<i>Acetone</i>	0.6004	<i>d</i>	+265.1	+269.2	+305.6	+590.9
	0.5476	<i>l</i>	-261.8	-266.3	-308.7	-596.9
		mean	263.5	267.8	307.2	593.9
<i>Ether</i>	0.6036	<i>d</i>	+282.1	+293.9	+336.1	+672.2
	0.5524	<i>l</i>	-280.9	-290.3	-336.7	-673.5
		mean	281.5	292.1	336.4	672.6
<i>Benzene</i>	0.6084	<i>d</i>	+289.6	+295.6	+337.5	+681.1
	0.5624	<i>l</i>	-282.6	-291.6	-337.0	-689.5
		mean	286.1	293.6	337.3	685.3
<i>Chloroform</i>	0.6080	<i>d</i>	+299.7	+305.9	+335.7	+705.5
	0.6128	<i>l</i>	-293.4	-301.3	-354.9	-701.8
		mean	296.6	303.6	355.3	703.7

TABLE III.

o-Iodophenyliminocamphor.

Solvent.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Dextro, laevo, or mean.	[M]		
			Na _D	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}
Ether	0.6780	<i>d</i>	+633.3°	+703.7°	+863.4°
	0.6716	<i>l</i>	-639.5	-707.8	-863.6
		mean	636.4	705.8	863.5
Ethyl alcohol	0.6700	<i>d</i>	+663.0	+736.9	+903.8
	0.6760	<i>l</i>	-656.9	-743.9	-912.0
		mean	660.0	740.4	907.9
Chloroform	(<i>α</i>) 0.7204	<i>d</i>	+748.7	+781.8	+976.0
	(<i>β</i>) 0.7200	<i>d</i>	+762.0	+795.4	+989.2
	(<i>γ</i>) 0.7228	<i>d</i>	+758.7	+789.3	+985.2
Acetone	0.6756	<i>d</i>	+771.4	+896.4	+1106
	0.6612	<i>l</i>	-779.8	-904.6	-1113
		mean	775.6	900.5	1110
Methyl alcohol $[\alpha] = \frac{36.72}{\lambda^2 - 0.1446}$; [M] = 3.67[α] ; λ ₀ = 0.3803.					
(<i>γ</i>) m.p. 96°-67°	0.7220	<i>d</i> (obs.)	+693.8°	+739.8°	+915.0
Calc.			693.8	741.4	914.9
Diff.			±0	-1.6	+0.1
(<i>β</i>) m.p. 93°	0.7200	<i>d</i> (obs.)	+693.5	+736.5	+915.0
Calc.			693.8	741.4	914.9
Diff.			-0.3	-4.9	+0.1
(<i>α</i>) m.p. 86°-87°	0.7228	<i>d</i> (obs.)	+690.9	+736.5	+914.2
Calc.			693.8	741.4	914.
Diff.			-2.9	-4.9	-0.7
Benzene $[\alpha] = \frac{41.38}{\lambda^2 - 0.1596}$; [M] = 3.67[α] ; λ ₀ = 0.3995.					
(<i>γ</i>) m.p. 96°-97°	0.4860	<i>d</i> (obs.)	+808.2°	+864.8	+1095.0
Calc.			809.9	870.5	1095.0
Diff.			-1.7	-5.7	0
(<i>β</i>) m.p. 93°	0.7232	<i>d</i> (obs.)	+809.8	+870.6	+1093.5
Calc.			809.9	870.5	1095.0
Diff.			-0.1	+0.1	-1.5
(<i>α</i>) m.p. 86°-87°	0.7244	<i>d</i> (obs.)	+810.6	+869.2	+1092.0
Calc.			809.9	870.5	1095.0
Diff.			+0.7	-1.3	-3.0

TABLE IV.

o-Iodophenylaminocamphor.

Solvent.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.	[M]			
		N_{a_D}	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}	Hg _{vio.}
<i>Benzene</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{9.79}{\lambda^2 - 0.0762}$; [M] = 3.69 [α] ; $\lambda_0 = 0.2760$.				
Dextro (obs.)	0.6648	+133.2°	+141.6°	+163.8°	+316.4°
Calc.		133.4	140.1	162.8	317.5
Diff.		-0.2	+1.5	+1.0	-1.1
<i>Methyl alcohol</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{12.02}{\lambda^2 - 0.0554}$; [M] = 3.69 [α] ; $\lambda_0 = 0.2354$.				
Dextro (obs.)	0.6542	+152.1	+157.7	+183.1	+329.5
Calc.		152.25	159.2	182.8	329.7
Diff.		-0.15	-1.5	+0.3	-0.2
<i>Ethyl alcohol</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{13.74}{\lambda^2 - 0.0544}$; [M] = 3.69 [α] ; $\lambda_0 = 0.2332$.				
Dextro	0.6596	+173.45	+181.8	+209.75	+385.9
Laevo	0.2560	-173.0	-180.1	-209.0	-360.25
Mean (obs.)		173.2	181.0	209.4	373.8
Calc.		173.3	181.3	208.0	374.0
Diff.		-0.1	-0.2	+1.4	+0.2
<i>Acetone</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{14.62}{\lambda^2 - 0.0581}$; [M] = 3.69 [α] ; $\lambda_0 = 0.2410$.				
Dextro	0.6654	+188.2	+196.55	+224.25	+412.4
Laevo	0.6592	-184.7	-195.9	-221.1	-404.1
Mean (obs.)		186.5	196.2	222.7	408.3
Calc.		186.6	195.4	224.6	409.0
Diff.		-0.1	+0.8	-1.9	-0.7
<i>Ether</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{14.91}{\lambda^2 - 0.0705}$; [M] = 3.69 [α] ; $\lambda_0 = 0.2655$.				
Dextro (obs.)	0.6652	+199.6	+208.0	+238.5	463.0
Calc.		198.85	208.6	241.5	+460.2
Diff.		+0.75	-0.6	-3.0	+2.8
<i>Chloroform</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{17.73}{\lambda^2 - 0.0675}$; [M] = 3.69 [α] ; $\lambda_0 = 0.2598$.				
Dextro	0.6676	+234.9	+246.1	+287.4	-
Laevo	0.6592	-232.3	-243.5	-282.7	-532.1
Mean (obs.)		233.6	244.8	285.1	532.1
Calc.		234.0	245.4	283.7	534.2
Diff.		-0.4	-0.6	+1.4	-2.1

TABLE V.

m-Iodophenyliminocamphor.

Solvent.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Dextro, leavo, or mean.	[M]		
			Na _D	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}
Ether	0.6904	<i>d</i>	+ 1161°	+ 1284°	+ 1603°
	0.7156	<i>l</i>	- 1164	- 1279	- 1601
		mean	1163	1282	1602
Acetone	0.6208	<i>d</i>	+ 1303	+ 1354	+ 1662
	0.6136	<i>l</i>	- 1307	- 1349	- 1666
		mean	1305	1352	1664
Chloroform	0.6944	<i>d</i>	+ 1324	+ 1388	+ 1773
	0.6984	<i>l</i>	- 1329	- 1390	- 1769
		mean	1327	1389	1771
<i>Methyl alcohol</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{63.95}{\lambda^2 - 0.1581};$		$[M] = 367[\alpha];$	$\lambda_0 = 0.3951$	
Dextro	0.7376		+ 1229	+ 1319	+ 1652
Leavo	0.7304		- 1231	- 1321	- 1648
Mean (obs.).			1230	1320	1650
Calc.			1229	1319	1652
Diff.			+ 1	+ 1	- 2
<i>Ethyl alcohol</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{71.75}{\lambda^2 - 0.1439}$		$[M] = 3.67[\alpha];$	$\lambda_0 = 0.3793.$	
Dextro	0.7264		+ 1299	+ 1379	+ 1712
Leavo	0.7160		- 1302	- 1371	- 1707
Mean (obs.).			1301	1375	1710
Calc.			1295	1384	1706
Diff.			+ 6	- 9	+ 4
<i>Benzene</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{74.53}{\lambda^2 - 0.1544};$		$[M] = 3.67[\alpha];$	$\lambda_0 = 0.3929$	
Dextro	0.7192		+ 1421	+ 1520	+ 1905
Leavo	0.7040		- 1416	- 1514	- 1908
Mean (obs.)			1419	1517	1907
Calc.			1418	1522	1902
Diff.			+ 1	- 5	+ 5

TABLE VI.

m-Iodophenylaminocamphor.

Solvent.	Concentration : g/100 c. c.	Dextro, leavo, or mean.	[M]			
			Na _D	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}	Hg _{vio.}
Acetone	0.7492	<i>d</i>	+244.0°	+290.8°	+325.4°	+586.7°
	0.6784	<i>l</i>	-252.8	-285.4	-320.8	-595.4
		mean	248.4	288.1	323.1	591.0
Chloroform	0.6500	<i>d</i>	+312.2	+351.9	+405.8	+817.4
	0.6860	<i>l</i>	-317.4	-349.5	-404.1	-814.7
		mean	314.8	351.7	405.0	186.1
Benzene	0.6816	<i>d</i>	+322.1	+341.1	+406.1	+833.9
	0.6848	<i>l</i>	-312.5	-344.8	-404.1	-824.3
		mean	317.3	343.0	405.1	829.1
Ether	0.6972	<i>d</i>	+330.8	+344.0	+420.8	+831.0
	0.6888	<i>l</i>	-329.5	-348.1	-416.9	-830.5
		mean	330.1	346.1	418.9	830.8
<i>Methyl alcohol</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{21.28}{\lambda^2 - 0.0392}$; [M] = 3.69[α]; λ ₀ = 0.1980					
Dextro	0.6456	+254.4	+265.8	+300.3	+520.2	
Leavo	0.6904	-253.9	-264.5	-299.3	-526.5	
Mean (obs.)		254.1	265.1	299.8	523.3	
Calc.		255.0	266.25	303.15	520.7	
Diff.		-0.9	-1.15	-3.35	+2.6	
<i>Ethyl alcohol</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{19.73}{\lambda^2 - 0.0682}$; [M] = 3.69[α]; λ ₀ = 0.2612					
Dextro	0.7008	+263.2	+276.5	+318.9	+597.5	
Leavo	0.6920	-258.7	-269.3	-314.7	-599.9	
Mean (obs.)		261.0	272.9	316.8	598.7	
Calc.		261.0	273.75	316.5	597.3	
Diff.		±0	-0.85	+0.3	+1.4	

TABLE VII.

Solvent.	Concentration : g/100 c. c.	Dextro, leavo, or mean.	[M]		
			Na _D	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}
<i>p-Iodophenyliminocamphor.</i>					
Ether	0.7072	<i>d</i>	+1517°	+1650°	+2081°
	0.6956	<i>l</i>	-1523	-1644	-2079
		mean	1520	1647	2080
Methyl alcohol	0.6676	<i>d</i>	+1575	+1721	+2166
	0.6936	<i>l</i>	-1580	-1720	-2162
		mean	1578	1721	2164
Acetone	0.7104	<i>d</i>	+1592	+1679	+2120
	0.6748	<i>l</i>	-1581	-1684	-2124
		mean	1587	1682	2122
<i>Ethyl alcohol</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{84.95}{\lambda^2 = 0.1589}$; [M] = 3.67[α] ; λ ₀ = 0.3986.				
Dextro	0.6816		+1624	+1732	+2190
Leavo	0.6644		-1621	-1732	-2196
Mean (obs.)			1623	1732	2193
Calc.			1619	1740	2187
Diff.			+4	-8	+6
<i>Chloroform</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{88.88}{\lambda^2 = 0.1613}$ [M] = 3.67 [α] ; λ ₀ = 0.4016.				
Dextro	0.6816		+1764	+1880	+2383
Leavo	0.6828		-1755	-1879	-2376
Mean (obs.)			1760	1880	2380
Calc.			1753	1888	2383
Diff.			+7	-8	-8
<i>Benzene</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{86.51}{\lambda^2 = 0.1691}$; [M] = 3.67 [α] ; λ ₀ = 0.4112.				
Dextro	0.6780		+1781	+1927	+2462
Leavo	0.6660		-1772	-1923	-2461
Mean (obs.)			1777	1925	2462
Calc.			1782	1924	2459
Diff.			-5	+1	+8

TABLE VIII.

p-Iodophenylaminocamphor.

Solvent.	Concentration : g/100 c. c.	Dextro, levo or mean.	[M]			
			N_{a_D}	$H_{yel.}$	$H_{g_{gr.}}$	$H_{g_{vio.}}$
Methyl alcohol	0.6824	<i>d</i>	+202.8°	+235.3°	+262.3°	+440.8°
	0.6800	<i>l</i>	-206.2	-233.3	-263.2	-444.3
		mean	204.5	234.3	262.8	442.6
Ethyl alcohol	0.6612	<i>d</i>	+214.8	+234.5	+267.9	+446.4
	0.6628	<i>l</i>	-216.0	-236.6	-264.4	-453.7
		mean	210.4	235.6	266.2	450.1
Acetone	0.6684	<i>d</i>	+242.9	+256.6	-300.8	+455.4
	0.6792	<i>l</i>	-244.4	-252.5	-296.0	-456.2
		mean	243.7	254.6	298.4	455.8
Benzene	0.6640	<i>d</i>	+241.7	+277.8	+313.9	+622.3
	0.6660	<i>l</i>	-249.3	-279.8	-318.5	-626.2
		mean	245.5	278.8	316.2	624.3
<i>Ether</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{18.66}{\lambda^2 - 0.0779}$; [M] = 3.69 [α] ; $\lambda_0 = 0.2791$.					
Dextro	0.6624	+256.3	+272.9	+309.1	+615.8	
Laevo	0.6620	-250.8	-275.8	-306.6	-624.1	
Mean (obs.)			256.6	274.4	307.9	619.8
Calc.			256.3	269.3	313.2	615.4
Diff.			-2.7	+5.1	-5.3	+4.4
<i>Chloroform</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{21.11}{\lambda^2 - 0.0670}$; [M] = 3.69 [α] ; $\lambda_0 = 0.2588$.					
Dextro	0.7140		+271.3	+284.2	+330.8	+643.3
Laevo	0.6604		-265.4	-282.1	-329.6	-642.4
Mean (obs.)			268.4	283.2	330.2	642.9
Calc.			278.0	291.6	337.0	633.3
Diff.			-9.6	-8.4	-6.8	+9.6

TABLE IX.

Acetyl Derivative of p-Iodophenylaminocamphor.

Solvent : *Chloroform* $[\alpha] = \frac{7.017}{\lambda^2}$; $[M] = 4.11[\alpha]$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
4.0016	—	—	Hg ₄₃₅₈	+36.94°	-0.10	+36.84°	4.0020
	-30.36°	-0.09°	Cd ₄₈₀₀	30.45	+0.03	30.48	
	-27.17	+0.04	Cd ₅₀₈₆	27.13	-0.09	27.04	
	-25.86	±0.0	Ag ₅₃₀₉	25.86	-0.13	25.73	
	-23.49	-0.05	Hg ₅₄₆₁	23.54	+0.07	23.61	
	-21.00	-0.01	Hg ₅₇₈₀	21.01	+0.09	21.10	
	-20.24	+0.02	Na ₅₈₉₃	20.22	±0	20.23	
	-18.86	+0.03	Li ₆₁₀₄	18.83	+0.16	18.99	
	-16.87	-0.07	Cd ₆₄₃₈	16.94	-0.08	16.86	
	-15.74	+0.14	Li ₆₇₀₈	15.60	-0.01	15.61	

TABLE X.

Camphorquinone.

Solvent.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.	$[M]$		
		Na _D	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}
<i>Benzene</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{13.80}{\lambda^2 - 0.2199}$;	$[M] = 1.66[\alpha]$;	$\lambda_0 = 0.4689.$	
Dextro	1.0392	-180.4°	-198.9°	-293.9°
Laevo	1.0320	+181.2	+198.7	+293.5
Mean (obs.)		180.8	198.8	293.7
Calc.		180.0	200.5	292.4
Diff.		+0.8	-1.7	+1.3
<i>Acetone</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{13.73}{\lambda^2 - 0.2200}$;	$[M] = 1.66[\alpha]$;	$\lambda_0 = 0.4690.$	
Dextro	1.248	-180.7	-198.6	-293.6
Laevo	1.0192	+179.9	+197.8	+293.2
Mean (obs.)		180.3	198.2	293.4
Calc.		179.4	199.7	291.5
Diff.		+0.9	-1.5	+1.9

TABLE X—(contd.).

Solvent.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.	[M]		
		Na _D	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr}
<i>Chloroform</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{12.99}{\lambda^2 - 0.2234}$;	$[M] = 1.66[\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.4727$.		
Dextro	1.1520	-175.1	-193.9	-288.8
Laevo	1.1568	+173.8	+194.4	+288.5
Mean (obs.)		174.45	194.15	288.65
Calc.		174.3	194.8	288.2
Diff.		+0.15	-0.65	+0.45
<i>Ether</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{12.15}{\lambda^2 - 0.2283}$;	$[M] = 1.66[\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.4778$		
Dextro	1.1356	-168.2	-190.4	-288.0
Laevo	1.1540	+170.5	+192.1	+287.3
Mean (obs.)		169.35	191.25	287.65
Calc.		169.5	190.6	288.5
Diff.		-0.15	+0.65	-0.86
<i>Ethyl alcohol</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{12.08}{\lambda^2 - 0.2254}$;	$[M] = 1.66[\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.4748$.		
Dextro	1.1844	-164.7	-185.2	-274.8
Laevo	1.1776	+164.3	+184.1	+274.9
Mean (obs.)		164.5	184.65	274.85
Calc.		164.6	184.5	275.5
Diff.		-0.1	+0.15	-0.65
<i>Methyl alcohol</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{7.98}{\lambda^2 - 0.2309}$;	$[M] = 1.66[\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.4805$.		
Dextro	1.1692	-113.6	-129.2	-197.3
Laevo	1.1368	+113.9	+128.5	+195.9
Mean (obs.)		113.75	128.85	196.4
Calc.		113.8	128.4	196.75
Diff.		-0.05	+0.45	-0.35

We wish to make grateful acknowledgment to the Government of Bihar and Orissa in the Ministry of Education for the grant of research scholarships to two of us (H. B.-M. and B. B.) which have enabled them to take part in this investigation. We also wish to acknowledge the valuable assistance which we received from Babu Indramani Mahanti, B.Sc., the Head Assistant of the Chemical Department.

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Received December 22, 1930.

OBITUARY NOTICE

ALFRED JOHN TURNER

Fellow

Elected—April 14, 1927

Deceased—March 15, 1931